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Historical Sciences

THE ROLE OF THE ODKB IN THE SYSTEM OF INTERNATIONAL SECURITY

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Abstract

The article discusses the main tasks for ensuring the national security of the states that are members of the ODKB, which is due to the need for stable development of society and respect for human rights. The problems that arose with the collapse of the USSR were superimposed on the processes of globalization and the threats and challenges associated with it (civil wars, the genocide of the Russian population in Ukraine, terrorism, organized transnational crime), which can only be eradicated if there is cooperation in the military-political sphere of the countries included in the ODKB.

Keywords: state, man, history, weapons, patriotism.

I. INTRODUCTION

The relevance of the study of regional institutions for ensuring modern international security is directly due to the fact that the universal security system (UN) is currently being reformed, which raises the question of adapting the UN to a serious change in the international political landscape that has occurred over more than six decades of its existence. This problem has become especially urgent due to the emergence of a dangerous tendency to use military force against sovereign states bypassing the UN. NATO's military actions against Yugoslavia, launched in March 1999 without the sanction of the Security Council, they clearly indicated the possibility of erosion of the role of the UN as the central element of the modern international political system. The answer to the question of what it will be depends on what regional security systems will be.

II. METHODOLOGY

The methodological bases of the study was an institutional approach that considers foreign policy institutions as a formal sphere of interstate relations. Universal and regional institutions for ensuring international security are considered as a system of institutions and organizations that regulate interstate relations with the help of material and ideal (symbolic means) and on the basis of fixed international legal norms.

The functioning of international security institutions is investigated within the framework of the paradigm of neorealism. The specificity and complexity of the study of the stated problem require the use of general scientific methods of political-legal, comparative, historical, system-structural and structural-functional analysis.

III. DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

In the context of globalization, the Russian Federation, its allies and partners are stepping up efforts to ensure international security in the post-Soviet space. In this context, the ODKB occupies a key place in a number of regional and sub-regional coordination organizations. The ODKB members are the Republic of Armenia, the Republic of Belarus, the Republic of Kazakhstan, the Kyrgyz Republic, the Russian Federation, and the Republic of Tajikistan.

The Concept of the Foreign Policy of the Russian Federation emphasizes that Russia considers the CSTO as one of the most important elements of the modern security system in the post-Soviet space. Russia stands for the qualitative development of the ODKB, its transformation into an authoritative multifunctional international organization capable of resisting modern challenges and threats in the face of the increasing impact of diverse global and regional factors in the ODKB area of responsibility and adjacent areas.

Thus, the doctrinal documents link the prospects for further development of the ODKB with its transformation in the external and internal spheres. In the external sphere, one of the priorities is to increase the role of the ODKB in international relations. The basis for the implementation of this direction is the UN's guidelines for cooperation with regional organizations, which it considers as elements of a new system of collective security in a world capable of resisting new challenges and threats. In the internal sphere, the most urgent tasks for the ODKB are the internal consolidation of the organization, increasing its cohesion and combat capability. An important connecting part of the internal and external sphere of transformation is diplomatic efforts to recognize the ODKB by the international community as a real military-political union responsible for a significant part of the Eurasian space.

Until today, the ODKB remains the only supranational factor in ensuring the sovereignty, security, and territorial integrity of its members in the Eurasian space.

The activities of the ODKB as an institution for ensuring international security are determined by the Concept agreed upon by the participating States, according to which the strategic goal of the ODKB member states is to prevent wars and armed conflicts, and in the event of their outbreak - guaranteed protection of the interests, sovereignty and territorial integrity of the participating states.

The ability of the ODKB to withstand modern VRO depends largely on the quality of the organization's management. In the structure of the military-political governing bodies of the model, three hierarchical levels of management can be distinguished. At the highest level, the leadership of the ODKB is carried out by the ODKB Collective Security Council at the level of heads of state, as well as the Permanent Council, the Secretariat and the Joint Headquarters of the ODKB.

At the middle level, there are advisory and executive bodies: the Council of Defense Ministers, the Council of Foreign Ministers, the Committee of Secretaries of Security Councils, the ODKB Military Committee and a number of subsidiary bodies (the Interstate Commission on Military-Technical Cooperation, several Coordinating Councils). At the lower level, there are Working groups and public structures (Analytical Association, University League, etc.). The command of military forces and means under the leadership of the ODKB Joint Staff is carried out by the corresponding command and staff structures of subordinate levels.

Thus, the ODKB has the full range of governing bodies at the political and military level, as well as the necessary structures for activities within the framework of public diplomacy.

The following features are characteristic of the ODKB as an international security organization:

- the right to collective defense enshrined in doctrinal documents in accordance with Article 4 of the Treaty;
- the presence of three regions of responsibility with the integrating role of Russia: Central, Transcaucasian and Central Asian;
- the presence of a Collective Rapid Reaction Force (CSR);
- The presence of a Peacekeeping Force (MC);
- a developed system of military-technical and military-economic cooperation of the participating countries;
- a system of cooperation with international and regional organizations;
- the right of veto.

The scale of the ODKB tasks determines the priority of steps to increase interstate economic and military-political integration in the post-Soviet space, to strengthen in the face of the ODKB a new constructive model of ensuring regional security as a basis for stable and sustainable development of independent states and respect for human rights.

Particular importance is attached to the institutionalization of military-political cooperation for the Central Asian States, whose military capabilities are in the process of formation.

As part of the transformation of the Organization, the following factors are taken into account, determining the direction of improving the capabilities of the ODKB as a model for ensuring collective security.

Firstly, Afghanistan remains a serious source of threats in the Eurasian region. Drug trafficking is carried out from this country, illegal armed groups infiltrate into the territory of neighboring states, illegal migration occurs, fundamentalist ideology is exported. A particular threat comes from the possible infiltration of ISIS militants from Afghanistan.

It is necessary to take into account the threats emanating from American technologies of organizing subversive actions in peacetime — color revolutions and hybrid wars. The ability to resist them requires the development of the ODKB crisis response system and the military component, improving the Organization's capabilities to counter threats in the field of information and cybersecurity, coordination in the field of countering terrorism, combating extremism, illegal migration, and cross-border organized criminal groups.

Taking into account the peculiarities of the "color revolutions" that have already been provoked in some ODKB states and can be used against them in the future, the ODKB approaches to the use of force in conflict resolution need to be improved. One of the urgent measures to counter the threat is to establish operational cooperation between the ODKB, the UN, the OSCE and some other subjects of international relations in order to form, in particular, an agreed point of view on the very concept of "aggression".

The strengthening of the military component should be accompanied by steps aimed at improving the procedures for deciding on the use of force in conflicts in order to prevent aggression against the ODKB countries. In this context, the decision-making process within the organization is imperfect.

It is necessary to properly link the duration of the consultation procedure with the practice adopted in the ODKB, when "the ratio of the allied obligations of the ODKB member states on a bilateral and collective basis will depend on what the position of the state subjected to aggression is." The wide range and rapidity of the subversive actions used during the color revolutions requires the development by the ODKB allies of an agreed concept of "aggression" in relation to the military-political realities of our time. In the absence of such a pre-agreed agreement, delay in consultations on assistance in the face of unpredictable political situations and high dynamics of conflict development can lead to negative consequences.

In accordance with the Joint Declaration on Cooperation between the ODKB and UN secretariats, the two organizations intend to cooperate in the fight against terrorism, transnational crime, illegal arms trade, conflict resolution, as well as emergency prevention and response to them. The priority task of further cooperation is to eliminate the threats facing the international community.

Meeting of the leaders of the ODKB countries 2022.

Fundamentally significant in the legal regulation of the ODKB peacekeeping activities is that "two modes of conducting peacekeeping operations are established within its framework: the first is conducting peacekeeping operations on the initiative of the ODKB, and the second is participation in peacekeeping operations of other regional organizations.

In the first case, after making a decision to conduct a peacekeeping operation, the Collective Security Council immediately informs the UN Security Council about it (if the operation is planned on the territory of a ODKB member state) or appeals to the UN Security Council with a request for an appropriate mandate to conduct a peacekeeping operation (when conducting a ODKB peacekeeping operation on the territory of other states).

In the second case (participation in peacekeeping operations of other regional organizations) These may be peacekeeping operations carried out on the basis of relevant decisions of the UN Security Council (Part 1 of Article 7), as well as peacekeeping operations of regional organizations carried out under their jurisdiction in accordance with the provisions of the UN Charter and not containing coercive actions, if there are legitimate decisions of regional organizations and the consent of the state to conduct an operation on its territory (part 2 of Article 7)".

IV. CONCLUSION

The heterogeneity of the development of the main components of integration processes, characteristic of almost the entire period of the existence of the CIS, affects the processes within the ODKB. Attention is drawn to this fact in a number of modern studies, where fundamental issues of bilateral cooperation between Russia and the CIS countries are analyzed, certain patterns in the development of mutual relations are deduced, factors both contributing to the strengthening of the ODKB and complicating cooperation within the Organization are mentioned.

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РОЛЬ ОДКБ В СИСТЕМЕ МЕЖДУНАРОДНОЙ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ

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Аннотация

В статье рассматриваются основные задачи по обеспечению национальной безопасности государств, входящих в ОДКБ, что обусловлено необходимостью стабильного развития общества и соблюдения прав человека. Проблемы, возникшие с распадом СССР, наложились на процессы глобализации и связанные с ней угрозы и вызовы (гражданские войны, геноцид русского населения на Украине, терроризм, организованная транснациональная преступность), искоренить которые можно только при наличии сотрудничества в военно-политической сфере стран, включенных в ОДКБ.

Ключевые слова: государство, человек, история, оружие, патриотизм.

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